

DMP: Exploring tumor-associated myeloid cell dynamics in response to alphavirus-driven immunomodulation

Version 1

Description

Data Management Plan (DMP)

Revision & Duration: The DMP will be regularly updated throughout the 36-month project.

Data Summary: The DMP outlines data collection objectives, formats, sources, estimated size, and relevance.

FAIR Data: The dataset will be shared in a public repository (e.g., GEO) with DOI-assigned metadata upon peer review and publication. Additional data will be available upon request from the corresponding author. Data will be structured hierarchically, with unique and versioned file names. Open access will be provided for anonymized data, while sensitive data will be restricted per legal requirements. Controlled remote access or on-site use will be possible. Required software includes OpenOffice, Adobe PDF Reader, image viewers, FlowJo, etc. Data and metadata will be archived for ten years.

Interoperability & Accessibility: Data will follow disciplinary standards, controlled vocabularies, and open formats. Data will be available upon publication, with some

accessible earlier via preprints. Quality assurance measures include validation, replication, and systematic bias control. Open formats ensure long-term usability unless the repository ceases operations.

Resource Allocation & Security: Project funds cover data management costs. The supervisor oversees updates, storage, and archiving. Long-term preservation does not involve additional institutional costs. Sensitive data will be encrypted, stored securely, and accessed only by authorized members under non-disclosure agreements. Automatic backups occur weekly, with manual checks every two months. Data will be preserved in a repository and institutional storage for ten years.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

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Researchers

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Organizations

LBMC

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: DMP: Exploring tumor-associated myeloid cell dynamics in response to alphavirus-driven immunomodulation

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: lzp-2024/1-0254

Project:

3. License

License: AFL-3.0

Access Rights: Restricted

Publication Date:

4. Templates

Descriptions

LCS FARP

Data Management Plan (DMP)

1. Summary of Data Generated

Purpose of Data Collection and Relation to Project:

This project will generate experimental data to investigate tumor-associated myeloid cell (MC) dynamics in response to alphavirus-driven immunomodulation. Data will support the study of MC recruitment, reprogramming, and immune responses in tumor microenvironments (TME).

Types and Format of Data Generated:

Experimental Data: Imaging (confocal microscopy, IVIS imaging), flow cytometry, transcriptomics (RNA-seq), proteomics (cytokine/chemokine profiling), functional assays (T-cell activation, phagocytosis).

Written Data: Manuscripts, patents, reports, scientific posters, public engagement materials.

Datasets: RNAseq, single-cell sequencing, proteomics, cytokine profiling, and in vivo tumor progression data.

Modeling Data: AI-driven analyses, dynamic modeling of MC interactions, MC reprogramming.

Re-use of Existing Data:

Where applicable, existing datasets (publicly available transcriptomics, proteomics, or tumor immune microenvironment studies) will be incorporated into the study for validation and comparative analysis.

Origin of Data:

Data will be collected from experimental models including in vivo murine tumor models, in vitro 3D co-cultures, and ex vivo tumor-infiltrating MC populations. Data sources will also include publicly available datasets for comparison and meta-analysis.

Expected Size of Data Collection:

Given the nature of imaging, transcriptomics, and proteomics data, the project is expected to generate several gigabytes (GB) of data.

2. FAIR Principles Compliance

2.1. Making Data Findable

Persistent identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) will be used for datasets and publications.

A structured naming convention for datasets will be followed, including project name, dataset type, experiment date, and version.

2.2. Openly Accessible Data

Most data will be deposited in open-access repositories upon peer-review publication (e.g., Zenodo, GEO, EMBL-EBI).

Certain datasets may be released later, depending on IP considerations. Embargoed Data: If patent protection is required, certain datasets may be embargoed until IP protection is secured.

Restricted Access Data: Sensitive data will not be openly available. Access to such data will be granted upon request and under data-sharing agreements.

2.3. Making Data Interoperable

Data will be stored in widely used formats such as .pzfx, .csv, .xlsx, .jpeg, .tiff, .fastq, .fcs, .sbml to ensure interoperability.

Metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies (e.g., MINSEQE for transcriptomics, FAIR principles) will be applied.

2.4. Making Data Reusable

Data will be stored in FAIR-compliant repositories to ensure accessibility and reusability.

Proper documentation (experimental protocols, software pipelines) will be provided to enable re-use.

3. Allocation of Resources

Data management activities will be funded through the project budget.

The project supervisor will oversee data management, ensuring compliance with FAIR principles.

Institutional resources (cloud storage) will be used for data storage and processing. Data archiving for ten years will be covered by institutional infrastructure without additional costs.

4. Data Security

Storage & Backup:

Data will be stored on institutional servers with weekly automated backups.

Offsite storage on a separate institutional server ensures redundancy.

Access Control:

Sensitive data will be stored in encrypted folders with password-protected access.

Access will be restricted to authorized project members under data-sharing agreements.

Cloud-based storage (e.g., Google Drive, institutional servers) will be used with restricted access settings.

Data Transfer:

Sensitive data access will require on-site visits or controlled remote processing.

5. Ethical Aspects

Compliance with Ethical Guidelines:

The project will comply with GDPR, national data protection laws, and institutional ethical guidelines.

All patient-related or personal data, if any, will be anonymized before sharing.

Data Sharing & Consent:

Data from human donors (if any) will be anonymized, and informed consent will be obtained before collection.

Ethical approval for data collection and sharing will be obtained from PVD.

6. Long-Term Preservation

Primary Data Storage: Institutional repositories will store data for at least ten years.

External Repositories: Relevant datasets will be deposited in disciplinary repositories (GEO, EMBL-EBI, Zenodo) for long-term preservation.

Data Retirement: In the event of repository shutdowns, alternative storage solutions will be identified to ensure continued access.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Purpose of Data Collection and Relation to Project:

This project will generate experimental data to investigate tumor-associated myeloid cell (MC) dynamics in response to alphavirus-driven immunomodulation. Data will support the study of MC recruitment, reprogramming, and immune responses in tumor microenvironments (TME).

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Experimental data
- Process produced data
- Other

Types and Format of Data Generated: Experimental Data: Imaging (confocal microscopy, IVIS imaging), flow cytometry, transcriptomics (RNA-seq), proteomics (cytokine/chemokine profiling), functional assays (T-cell activation, phagocytosis). Written Data: Manuscripts, patents, reports, scientific posters, public engagement materials. Datasets: RNAseq, single-cell sequencing, proteomics, cytokine profiling, and in vivo tumor progression data. Modeling Data: AI-driven analyses, dynamic modeling of MC interactions, Boolean network models for MC reprogramming. Re-use of Existing Data: Where applicable, existing datasets (publicly available transcriptomics, proteomics, or tumor immune

microenvironment studies) will be incorporated into the study for validation and comparative analysis. Origin of Data: Data will be collected from experimental models including in vivo murine tumor models, in vitro 3D co-cultures, and ex vivo tumor-infiltrating MC populations. Data sources will also include publicly available datasets for comparison and meta-analysis.

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- TIFF
- PNG
- MP3
- XLS
- JPG
- Others

.docx, .pzfx, .fcs

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Data will be stored in FAIR-compliant repositories to ensure accessibility and reusability.

Proper documentation (experimental protocols, software pipelines) will be provided to enable re-use.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Data will be stored on institutional servers with weekly automated backups.

Offsite storage on a separate institutional server ensures redundancy.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Most data will be deposited in open-access repositories upon peer-reviewed publication(e.g., Zenodo, GEO, EMBL-EBI).

Data will be made available upon publication. Certain datasets may be released later depending IP considerations.

Embargoed Data: If patent protection is required, certain datasets may be embargoed until IP protection is secured.

Restricted Access Data: Sensitive data will not be openly available. Access to such data will be granted upon request and under data-sharing agreements.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

related software

FlowJo

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

Data will be stored in widely used formats such as .csv, .xlsx, .jpeg, .tiff, .fastq, .fcs, .sbml to ensure interoperability.

Metadata schemas and controlled vocabularies (e.g., MIAME for transcriptomics, FAIR principles) will be applied.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Data will be stored in FAIR-compliant repositories to ensure accessibility and reusability.

Proper documentation (experimental protocols, software pipelines) will be provided to enable re-use.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-03-09

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

EUR

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

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Data management activities will be funded through the project budget.

The project supervisor will oversee data management, ensuring compliance with FAIR principles.

Institutional resources (cloud storage) will be used for data storage and processing. Data archiving for ten years will be covered by institutional infrastructure without additional costs.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

institutional resources

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Other

Storage & Backup:

Data will be stored on institutional servers with daily automated backups.

Offsite storage on a separate institutional server ensures redundancy.

Access Control:

Sensitive data will be stored in encrypted folders with password-protected access.

Access will be restricted to authorized project members under data-sharing agreements.

Cloud-based storage (e.g., Google Drive, institutional servers) will be used with restricted access settings.

Data Transfer:

Sensitive data access will require on-site visits or controlled remote processing.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

animal experiments

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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